

Key points

[3D-image guided; economy; navigated; osteosynthesis; procedural costs; sacral fragility fracture; reimbursement; resource consumption; sacroplasty; screw fixation]

1. In a prospective mono-centric clinical study including 52 patients who underwent 3D-image-guided sacral screw fixation with (II) or without additional sacroplasty (I) for immobilizing, non-displaced sacral fragility fractures, differences in operative time, procedural radiation dose, implant costs and reimbursement were investigated.
2. Procedural 2D- ($p \approx 0.24$), and 3D-radiation dose ($p \approx 0.55$) were not significantly different between study groups.
3. Additional sacroplasty resulted in significantly expanded operative time ($p \approx 0.01$), 2D-fluoroscopy time ($p \approx 0.004$), and material costs ($p < 0.00001$), but also reimbursement ($p \approx 0.006$), according to the German inpatient reimbursement system.

Summary of results

Differences between groups were significant concerning surgical time, fluoroscopy time, implant costs, and reimbursement (significance level $p < 0.05$, Student's t-test)

NSF indicates navigation-assisted screw fixation; ASP, additional sacroplasty; 95% CI, 95% confidence interval; n.s., not significant

Result	NSF (n=26)	NSF+ASP (n=26)	p-level
Surgical duration, mean [95% CI] (minutes)	96 [83, 109]	119 [109, 129]	$p \approx 0.01$
3D-radiation dose, mean [95% CI] (mGycm)	842 [577, 1107]	735 [513, 957]	$p \approx 0.55$, n.s.
2D-radiation dose, mean [95% CI] (mGycm ²)	5950 [4131, 7768]	7706 [5483, 9928]	$p \approx 0.24$, n.s.
Fluoroscopy time, mean [95% CI] (seconds)	32.7 [27.1, 38.3]	46.6 [39.6, 53.6]	$p \approx 0.004$
Implant costs, mean [95% CI] (€/surgery)	204.34 [175.75, 232.93]	668.68 [585.20, 752.16]	$p < 0.00001$
Reimbursement, mean [95% CI] (€/surgery)	6584.49 [5826.23, 7342.75]	8416.01 [7427.07, 9404.95]	$p \approx 0.006$

Take Home Messages

1. In navigation-assisted iliosacral screw fixation procedures, additional sacroplasty allows for significantly higher reimbursement compared to similar procedures without additional sacroplasty, promoting a positive economic effect within the German inpatient reimbursement system.
2. However, higher financial reimbursements have to be offset against extended operative and 2D-fluoroscopy time, and increased material costs.
3. Based on average productivity expenses, additional sacroplasty was not confirmed to be economic despite higher associated remuneration.